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Abstract

The article elaborates major criteria that determine effective language acquisition. Quality of the education is synchronically related to learning criteria. Visibility and responsibility are considered very vital criteria for effective language acquisition. We should learn the process of foreign language learning more profoundly to provide a wider range of learning outcomes. The procedures, learning atmosphere and outcomes are interrelated in any learning process. The quality of the outcomes is up to the type of procedures and the learners' learning experience. For this reason, investing pedagogical expertise in the educational process also involves an investment in the quality of learning outcomes. There are more criteria which help language comprehension deeply.

Keywords: effective, language acquisition, criteria, skills, competent, comprehension

INTRODUCTION

There are some criteria that have positive impact on the effectiveness of language acquisition. Responsibility and visibility can be considered main factors in effective language learning. We are usually prone to think that the outcome of the language learning is the student's communication competence that can be evaluated by means of different performances and proficiency tests. Competent and valid communicative performance examination provides an important assessment of the language learner's communicative skills [5]. One can find popular distinctions in the learners' language skills and competent testing procedures can reveal such distinctions.

Nevertheless, focusing on skills-oriented proficiency tests lacks numerous other vital outcomes which are obvious, especially in the aims of teaching languages for the student independence and communicative inter-cultural competence. Inter-cultural competence is built up on communicative competence. However, communicative competence is related firstly to the language speaker's skills and knowledge in interactive situations, inter-cultural competence also concentrates on social and personal capabilities of the language user. Then it underlines the significance of linking to otherness and foreignness in human meetings. It underrates the tolerance of ambiguity and respect for difference in inter-cultural relations that depend on expectations and situation-specific cultural norms [8].

Social and personal learning appropriate for the purposes of inter-cultural competence are invisible in the proficiency tests which are conducted by external examination boards or testing agencies. We should learn the process of foreign language learning more profoundly to provide a wider range of learning outcomes. The procedures, learning atmosphere and outcomes are interrelated in any learning process. The quality of the outcomes is up to the type of procedures and the learners' learning experience. For this reason, investing pedagogical expertise in the educational process also involves an investment in the quality of learning outcomes. There are more criteria which help language comprehension deeply. One of these criteria is visibility in language learning process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are a myriad of studies regarding effective language acquisition conducted by researchers among whom we can find Akbari Z, Beattie M, Brown H, Babayev J, Carver D. J, Lehtovaara J, Kohonen V, Jaatinen R, Lamendella T, Muchiri M. N, Njogu K, Scovel T, Swain M, Trim J and many others. The topic of effective language learning or acquisition has always been an actual topic for language learners and teachers. Different hypotheses have been set forth about effective solution on this topic. However, research on the so-called topic is still being carried out by famous scholars who make a rigid research on the very topic.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION

Being responsible for language learning

Developing learner autonomy while learning a foreign language needs time, pedagogical skill and responsibility for self-study learning. This can be fulfilled through online and offline learning [3], [4]. As David Little shows, learners don't become autonomous students just being told that they are liable for their learning. They might manage more aspects of the learning process till they get adequate knowledge, motivation and skills. In order to take responsibility of their learning and improve their skills they should actively be involved in the complete learning process. Leslie Dickenson suggests to develop independent learning for the broader range of knowledge, skills and attitudes which the teacher should work on with the learners:

1. To justify and legitimize autonomy as a learning aim and to encourage the students to take a more independent approach to the learning process.

2. To convince the learners that they are able to assume autonomy if they make a strict attempt to learn something by assisting them gain successful experience.

3. To assist them to comprehend the language as a linguistic system and improve their communicative skills.

4. To contribute the students to comprehend a lot about the language learning and improve awareness of what is involved in the learning process.

5. To enable them to tackle emerging challenges in interaction and learning and overcome the impediments .

6. To help the learners to boost obvious learning strategies to make a plan, monitor and reflect on their learning.

7. To provide the learners with concrete opportunities to experience bigger independence in their language acquisition.

Visibility in language learning

What is meant by visibility is that language tests bring about language comprehension which makes the students understand the language with receptive tests and then the students make themselves understand them with productive tests. When language tests are given, especially to many test takers simultaneously including school leaving tests, the restrictions of economical and reliable scoring mean that the types of the tests involve mainly cognitive skills and narrow language which include gap-filling tests, multiple choice questions and open tests [6].

While standard tests give important information about the skills assessed, they can have a less desirable pedagogical wash-back effect which has been carried out previously. For understandable reasons, the teachers are forced to train their students to pass the test with excellent marks. Moreover, the capacity of standard tests to provide useful data for pedagogical learner guidance is also restricted depending on the open-endedness of the tests employed [11].

Learning a language inherently involves numerous private features and process-related learning outcomes which are educationally assessable language learning purposes in the language curriculum. In most national contexts, these educational purposes are also represented in curricular frameworks demanding all the teachers to imply them in their subject curriculum. This underlines the aims of improving a holistic learner development, learning responsible moral and social education [10]. For learning a foreign language, particularly a natural purpose is to develop inter-cultural language competence underlining the language speaker's ability to meet otherness respecting cultural difference.

It is vital to stress that the learners inevitably bring their own histories or autobiographies to classes.

These autobiographies reflect personal features, beliefs and assumptions of the language and learning that have emerged as a part of their learning history in their families and at school. These properties develop in relation with the affective, cognitive and social language learning processes [7]. They have a negative impact on the learner's observable language performance. While they are mainly invisible, especially in the paper-and-pencil tests, they have some features which are important for the improvement of language competence and motivation:

a) Liability to and mastery of one's language learning

b) Ambiguity tolerance and indefiniteness in communicative environment and language learning in general

c) Willingness to venture in order to manage communicative tasks and situation.

d) Comprehension of yourself as a language learner and user from the perspective of beliefs about language employment and you role as a student.

e) Attitudes and skills for socially liable, negotiated learning and language usage.

f) Learning strategies and skills important for consistent increasingly autonomous language learning carried out in the social student communities and in communication with other students and teacher.

g) A reflective main orientation to language learning with skills for critical self-evaluation and peer-reflection.

Features such as these are important for developing student independence, inter-cultural interaction and learner's own development [5]. They are an integral part of the pedagogical learning process in any language classroom, irrespective of the extent to which we know them as teachers [10]. To develop foreign language knowledge, we should heed more professional attention to such features.

In most cases, above-mentioned student features are not seen in external testing and may be inferred only indirectly from the learner's linguistic output information [1]. They can remain consciously unreachable to the learners in the process of learning until we render an explicit attention to them. Thus, they make up the so-called confidential, invisible curriculum of which learners have a peripheral awareness. The learners can have hardships in guaranteeing a conscious reflection and evaluation of language learning without awareness of learning means for them in their own views [2]. Likewise, the teachers can find it hard to conceptualize their role as mediators in student learning. It can be hard to negotiate the procedures, to provide teaching and assess the total range of learning outcomes without sharing the concepts to speak about. Students and teachers, for this reason, need a denominator language and concrete methods for the pedagogical teaching, monitoring and language learning reflection.

CONCLUSION

It is important to demonstrate what we mean by the concept of learning outcomes in learning a language targeted at consolidating student autonomy. We should attentively take into consideration how we realize appropriate notions in cultural meanings and how we can teach them to the learners. This type of thinking and re-examination is important during the learning process with the same student groups since the opportunities will change during the work course. For this reason, it is advisable to clear up professional comprehension of the key "what" question at relevant intervals also basing our presentations on actual observation and information obtained from concrete learning environment and papers. It is also essential to conduct regular pedagogical discussions in supportive teacher staff [9].

The above-mentioned features naturally exist in language classes in various national and regional meanings. For this reason, any pedagogical progress work should be undertaken within regional, national and local contexts. The research is launched, carried out and assessed by national experts.

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